

HIPPARCOS

Parameters for Uniform Revolving Scanning

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SUMMARY

Some considerations towards optimizing the scanning parameters are given. It is shown that the number of revolutions per year (K) should be chosen from a limited set of values depending on the mission duration. For 2.5 year duration the most favourable values are $K = 6.4, 6.8, 7.2,$ and 7.6 . The corresponding minimum values of the revolving angle are $\xi = 40.6, 38.2, 36.0,$ and 34.1 degrees. For good sky uniformity and maximum overlap of consecutive scans one is not free to choose ξ arbitrarily.

INTRODUCTION

The position of the nominal spin axis (z) can, for *any* scanning law, be related to that of the sun (s) by two angles,

$$\xi = \hat{s}z \text{ ('revolving angle')}, 0 \leq \xi \leq \xi_{\max} \sim 45^\circ, \quad (1)$$

$$v = \hat{e}sz \text{ ('revolving phase')}, 0 \leq v < 360^\circ, \quad (2)$$

cf. Fig. 1.

Revolving scanning is characterized by

$$\xi \simeq \text{constant}, \quad (3)$$

$$v = v_0 + v_1 t, \quad (4)$$

$$v_1 \sim \text{constant}. \quad (5)$$

Uniform revolving scanning is further characterized by

$$v \simeq \text{constant}, \quad (6)$$

where v is the speed (e.g. in rad/s) of the z axis with respect to the stars.

The concept of uniform revolving scanning was introduced by Høg (Note 24, 1978 Jan 13), who pointed out that (6) could be approximately satisfied with a simple harmonic modulation of v_1 . A further investigation was made by Hoyer (1979 Jan 29), and the scanning laws have also been discussed by Vaghi (M.A.O Working Paper No. 137, 1981 Jan). The present note contains some additional considerations which may be useful for the selection of scanning parameters for simulations and the real mission.

GENERAL RESULTS

Let (λ_z, β_z) be the ecliptical coordinates of z and $(\lambda_s, 0)$ those of the sun. We have then from the spherical triangle snz ,

$$\sin \beta_z = \sin \xi \sin \nu, \quad (7)$$

$$\cos \xi = \cos \beta_z \cos(\lambda_z - \lambda_s), \quad (8)$$

$$\sin \xi \cos \nu = \cos \beta_z \sin(\lambda_z - \lambda_s). \quad (9)$$

The coordinates of z are thus computed from ξ , ν , and λ_s by means of

$$\beta_z = \arcsin(\sin \xi \sin \nu), \quad (10)$$

$$\lambda_z = \lambda_s + \arctan(\tan \xi \cos \nu). \quad (11)$$

The speed of z with respect to the stars, v , can be written in terms of its components along λ and β ,

$$v^2 = (\dot{\lambda}_z \cos \beta_z)^2 + (\dot{\beta}_z)^2, \quad (12)$$

where $\dot{} \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$ symbolizes time derivatives. If both ξ and ν are continuous and differentiable we obtain

$$v^2 = (\dot{\lambda}_s \cos \nu + \dot{\xi})^2 + (\dot{\nu} \sin \xi - \dot{\lambda}_s \cos \xi \sin \nu)^2. \quad (13)$$

Note that (13) is completely general and would be valid for any scanning law with smoothly varying ξ and ν .

In reality $\xi(t)$ may be determined by other considerations, such as power requirements or the desirability of keeping ξ constant (for reasons of thermal stability). Then a perfectly uniform scanning ($\nu = \text{constant}$) can easily be realized by varying ν according to the first-order differential equation

$$\nu = \nu_0 \text{ at } t = t_0 \text{ (beginning of mission),} \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{\nu} = \operatorname{cosec} \xi [v^2 - (\dot{\lambda}_s \cos \nu + \dot{\xi})^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} + \dot{\lambda}_s \cot \xi \sin \nu. \quad (15)$$

HIPPARCOS REVOLVING SCANNING
F=SCAN01 XI=.6660 AK= 6.8000
T0= .0 T1= 913.0 VAR= .0
.....
VIEW FROM LONG= 0, LAT= 20

HIPPARCOS REVOLVING SCANNING
F=SCAN00 XI=.6660 AK= 6.8000
T0= .0 T1= 913.0 VAR=1.0
.....
VIEW FROM LONG= 0, LAT= 20

HIPPARCOS REVOLVING SCANNING
F=SCAN01 XI=.6660 AK= 6.8000
T0= .0 T1= 913.0 VAR= .0
.....
VIEW FROM LONG= 270, LAT= 20

HIPPARCOS REVOLVING SCANNING
F=SCAN00 XI=.6660 AK= 6.8000
T0= .0 T1= 913.0 VAR=1.0
.....
VIEW FROM LONG= 270, LAT= 20

HIPPARCOS REVOLVING SCANNING
F=SCAN02 XI=.7084 AK= 6.4000
T0= .0 T1= 913.0 VAR=1.0
.....
VIEW FROM LONG= 0, LAT= 20

HIPPARCOS REVOLVING SCANNING
F=SCAN00 XI=.6660 AK= 6.8000
T0= .0 T1= 913.0 VAR=1.0
.....
VIEW FROM LONG= 0, LAT= 20

HIPPARCOS REVOLVING SCANNING
F=SCAN03 XI=.6285 AK= 7.2000
T0= .0 T1= 913.0 VAR=1.0
.....
VIEW FROM LONG= 0, LAT= 20